

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ZIMUTO****FIRST NAME: SHUPIKAYI****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. How does academic essay writing differ from other many types of essays?
 - All academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to other works and seek to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.¹**
 - They are nonfictional writing produced for the mass public as part of periodicals such as newspapers.
 - They are published quickly and can be written by anyone.
 - Academic articles use both formal and informal language with the author's name and credentials listed.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

2. Why does a writer need a particular style guide?
- To ensure clarity, coherence, and consistency in the writing processes and meet the acceptable standards of the client or publishing company.²**
 - To comply with requirements of academic and publishing institutions only.
 - To make the document attractive and properly formatted.
 - To ensure the essay is nonfictional.
3. Which expression is true about the relationship between the research topic, question, and significance of the study?
- I am working on X because I want to find out Y so that I can help others find Z.³**
 - The research topic, question, and study significance are the only major parts of a research paper.
 - In academic writing research topics, questions, and study significance are written simultaneously and should not be changed.
 - The thought through process of identifying the research topic, question, and study significance cannot be separated and this applies to informal publications only.
4. Which of the following statements are not true about research arguments?

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 40.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th Edition (Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, 2018), 28.

- In a research argument, your aim is to think up clever rhetorical strategies and win the argument so that you persuade readers to accept your claim regardless of how good or bad.⁴**
 - Research arguments are like conversations with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues as such, readers won't necessarily oppose your claims, although they might.
 - It is an amiable but thoughtful back-and-forth process that develops and tests the best case you and the reader can make together.
 - When you make a research argument, you must imagine both readers' questions and your answers, and therefore, you must lay out your reasons and evidence so that your readers can consider them.
5. Which statement is not true about why citation is important in academic writing?
- Citation ensures clarity, coherence, and consistency in the writing process and helps the writer to meet the acceptable standards of academic institutions.⁵**
 - Citation gives credit to writers when their ideas, facts, and words are used.
 - It assures the accuracy of facts and in so doing writers earn their readers' trust.
 - It helps readers follow and extend your research as many readers use sources cited in a research paper not to check its reliability only but to pursue their work.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 56-57.

⁵ Ibid., 139-140.

6. What are the main differences between the notes-bibliography style or notes style and author-date citation style?

In notes-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote it or refer to it and then cite the source of that quotation in a correspondingly numbered note that provides information about the source (author, title, and facts of publication) plus relevant page numbers while in author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it.⁶

Notes-bibliography style or notes style is used widely in the humanities and some social sciences while author-date style is used mostly in social sciences and the natural and physical sciences, however, both take the same format in presentation.

In notes style, if you cite the same text again, you can shorten subsequent notes while in author-date citations you must write the full citation repeatedly whenever you cite it again with footnotes.

The two are commonly referred to as Turabian or Chicago systems of citation.

7. Which of the following statements is not true about punctuation?

Sentences can be easily comprehended even without proper punctuation in any written communication.⁷

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 141-142.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 316-320.

- Commas are used to separate items in a list and are also used to set off non-essential clauses or phrases and to separate two independent clauses when joined by a coordinating conjunction.
 - Semicolon is stronger than a comma and marks a greater break in the continuity of a sentence and it connects two independent clauses or full sentences that are related in meaning.
 - Punctuation helps to organise ideas, clarify meaning, and convey tone and emphasis, and using correct punctuation is essential to effective communication and can greatly enhance the readability and clarity of written communication.
8. Which of the following statements comprehensively describes hypothesis in quantitative research?
- Hypotheses are based on research questions that are in turn based on the critical analysis of the theory and previous research presented in the literature review and all data analyses are guided directly by the hypotheses.**⁸
 - Some dissertation research, such as qualitative research, does not use hypotheses.
 - In the event there are multiple research questions and hypotheses, systematically number research questions and related hypotheses for easy reference later in the dissertation.
 - References are necessary for hypothesis.

⁸ Sampson, James P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 34-35.

9. Which statement is not true about the literature review?
- Literature review is discipline bound and should only cite literature from the fields of family systems, psychology, or social work.⁹**
 - It provides a comprehensive summary and analysis of existing research on your topic.
 - Literature review demonstrates your understanding of the research context and identifies gaps in the literature your research aims to fill.
 - Literature review should help the reader understand the variables that will be examined in the dissertation and provide justification for the research questions being explored in the dissertation.
10. In results discussions, which of the following statements is more important?
- Provide an interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research within the context of the literature review, using key citations from the review of the literature to support the interpretation of each hypothesis.¹⁰**
 - It is necessary to include all the literature reviews in interpreting the results.
 - The actual discussion portion of dissertations should range between two to five pages.
 - All findings including those that are not significant should be discussed.

⁹ Sampson, James P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 31-32.

¹⁰ Ibid., 56-58.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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